

Identification of Polymerase and Proofreading Exonuclease Domains in the DNA Polymerases IA, IB and Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerase of the Plant Chloroplasts

Peramachi Palanivelu *

Department of Molecular Microbiology, School of Biotechnology, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai – 625 021, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(03), 706–727

Publication history: Received on 09 February 2023; revised on 14 March 2023; accepted on 18 March 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.3.0455>

Abstract

Chloroplast plays a crucial role in all photosynthetic plants and converts the light energy to chemical energy. It is a semi-autonomous organelle and is mostly controlled by its own genome and partly by the nuclear imports. To replicate its own genome, it uses two DNA polymerases, viz. polymerases IA and IB. DNA polymerase IA showed 72.45% identity to polymerase IB, but only 35.35% identity to the *E. coli* DNA polymerase I. Multiple sequence alignment (MSA) analysis have shown that the DNA polymerases IA and IB and the *E. coli* DNA polymerase I possess almost identical active sites for polymerization and proofreading (PR) functions, suggesting their possible common evolutionary origin. The nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP) is imported from the nucleus and involves in the transcription of all the four subunits of the chloroplast RNA polymerase. The polymerase catalytic core of the DNA polymerases IA, IB and the NEP are remarkably conserved and is in close agreement with other DNA/RNA polymerases reported already, and possess a typical template-binding pair (-YG-), a basic catalytic amino acid (K) to initiate catalysis and a basic nucleotide selection amino acid R at -4 from K. The DNA polymerases IA and IB are very similar to prokaryotic DNA polymerases, except in possessing a zinc-binding motif (ZBM) in them, like the eukaryotic replicases. Interestingly, the PR exonucleases of all three polymerases belong to the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases. The DNA polymerases IA and IB belong to the DEDD(Y)-subfamily, whereas the NEP belongs to the DEDD(H)-subfamily.

Keywords: Chloroplast replication; DNA polymerase IA; DNA polymerase IB; Polymerase active sites; Chloroplast transcription; Nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase; Proofreading exonucleases; Exonuclease active sites

1. Introduction

DNA and RNA polymerases are crucial enzymes of life and, therefore, they are found in all living cells. They play an important role in not only maintaining the blue-print of life in all living cells but also in the control of gene expression at the transcription level. Therefore, understanding the structure, function, mechanism and regulation of these polymerases has been the primary goal of molecular biologists since its discovery. Interestingly, these polymerases are highly conserved in all kingdoms of life, from viruses to animals. [1, 2]. DNA polymerases essentially involve in the replication and repair of genomes in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes whereas RNA polymerases involve in transcription of genomes, i.e., the flow of genetic information from DNA to RNA. The organelles such as mitochondria and chloroplasts also use these enzymes for replication and repair, and transcription processes. Prokaryotes use a single type of DNA polymerase for replication, viz. DNA pol III, whereas the replication in eukaryotes is a complex process and they use three types of DNA polymerases for genome replication and repair, viz. DNA pol α , pol ϵ and pol δ [3]. Organelles such as mitochondria and chloroplasts use mostly a single type of replicase, viz. DNA pol γ and DNA pols IA and IB, respectively.

* Corresponding author: Peramachi Palanivelu

Transcriptions are performed by different types of RNA polymerases in prokaryotes and eukaryotes. Viruses contain two types of RNA polymerases, viz. DNA-dependent RNAPs (DdRps) and RNA-dependent RNAPs (RdRps), which are of single-subunit (SSU) types. Eubacteria and archaeobacteria employ a single type of RNA polymerase for all their transcription needs and it is a multi-subunit (MSU) type. However, eukaryotes use 5 different types of RNA polymerases (I-V), which are also of MSU type [4]. The chloroplast transcription in higher plants is performed by two types of RNA polymerases, i) plastid-encoded RNA polymerase (PEP), and ii) nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP). PEP is essentially a eubacterial-type MSU enzyme whose catalytic core subunits are encoded by the chloroplast genome itself, whereas NEP is a SSU enzyme which is of T7 bacteriophage-type. PEP is crucial for the biogenesis and maintenance of chloroplasts, but is controlled by the NEP and nuclear-encoded sigma factors (Figs. 1A and 1B) [5].

Both the DNA and RNA polymerases do make mistakes during the replication/transcription processes, but rarely. However, the mistakes are corrected promptly by the PR enzymes in both the cases. Based on the active site structures, the PR enzymes are classified into two major groups, viz. DEDD- and PHP- superfamilies. The DEDD-superfamily is the most common and there are mainly two types of DEDD-superfamily of PR exonucleases found in all biological systems which repair any error(s) that might occur during replication and transcription processes: One type of DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease (intrinsic type) is found in the same DNA/RNA polymerase polypeptide itself and functions as a multifunctional enzyme (e. g.), *E. coli* DNA pol I. The second type of PR exonuclease (extrinsic type) exists as a tightly associated subunit along with the polymerase subunits, in a multienzyme complex system (e.g.), bacterial DNA pols III, ExoNs of RdRps the SARS-Coronaviruses and the PA subunits of the RNA polymerases in human influenza viruses [1, 6, 7]. The DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease, the most common type of PR enzyme, consists of two subfamilies, viz. DEDD(Y) and DEDD(H), depending upon whether they employ an invariant Y or a H as the proton acceptor to initiate catalysis [8].

These two superfamilies are invariably found/associated with the DNA/RNA replicases and transcriptases to repair any error that might occur during the replication/transcription processes [8, 9]. The PHP-superfamily is not that common and has been reported mainly from the bacterial kingdom, but recently from the viral kingdom also by Palanivelu (7). For example, the PHP-superfamily is commonly found in the bacterial replicative DNA polymerases III (DNA pols III belong to the C-family polymerases), and in bacterial DNA polymerases X. (It is interesting to note, that the A- and B-families of the replicative polymerases are found both in prokaryotes and eukaryotes, but the C-family is found only in bacterial kingdom. All the three families are involved in genome replication and repair. Whereas the A-family polymerase possesses two exonuclease domains (3→5' and 5'→3' exonucleases), but the B-family polymerase possesses only one exonuclease domain, i.e., 3'→5' PR exonuclease domain) [10].

1.1. DNA Polymerases of Chloroplasts and their Roles in the Replication

Chloroplasts, an important organelle of all photosynthetic plants, house the photosynthetic enzyme systems that convert the light energy to chemical energy. Thus, they play a vital role not only in the primary carbon metabolism but also in the biosynthesis of fatty acids, amino acids, and tetrapyrroles. Therefore, chloroplast's function is indispensable throughout the life-cycle of plants and a compromised activity results in embryo lethality. Chloroplasts and mitochondria are semi-autonomous organelles and are considered descendants of endosymbiotic α -proteobacteria-like and cyanobacteria-like organisms, respectively. They possess their own genomes, and replication, transcription and translation machineries. Their genomes exist primarily as homogeneous circular DNA molecules and replicated by its own DNA polymerases. Although the replication mechanisms of these organellar genomes are poorly understood in photosynthetic plants, several enzymes related to its genome replication, such as DNA polymerases IA/IB, primase, replicative DNA helicase, DNA topoisomerase, single-strand DNA-binding proteins, RNase H and DNA ligase have been localized in chloroplasts.

Our understanding of plant organelle DNA replication is still very incomplete [11]. This is largely due to insufficient knowledge about their replication and repair enzymes, and their role(s). To date, two organellar DNA polymerases, IA and IB, resembling bacterial DNA Pol I, have been identified in chloroplasts [3,12]. The DNA polymerase and PR exonuclease active sites of 1A and 1B show similarity to the *E. coli* DNA pol I, but differ from the bacterial DNA polymerase by harbouring a typical zinc-binding motif (ZBM) like eukaryotic replicases. However, both DNA pol IA and IB have been shown to replicate the entire chloroplast genome with a greater efficiency than the microbial DNA pol I.

The importance and involvement of these two polymerases is proved by genetic analysis. The pol IB knockout plants were shown to have fewer genome copy numbers per organelle and grew slowly [13], and the Δ PolIB deletion mutant showed increased sensitivity to double-stranded DNA breaks, suggesting its predominant role in chloroplast DNA damage repair [14]. Parent et al [14] found that mutation of both genes was lethal, and thus, confirming an essential and redundant role for these two proteins. However, the mutation of a single gene was sufficient to cause a reduction

in the levels of DNA in both mitochondria and plastids. They also demonstrated that *pollb*, but not *polla* mutant lines, are hypersensitive to ciprofloxacin, a small molecule that specifically induces DNA double-strand breaks in plant organelles, suggesting a function for PolIB in DNA repair. MSA analysis shows that pol IA and pol IB are very similar to each other, and possess identical polymerase and PR exonuclease active sites (Figs. 2 and 3). Unlike the *E. coli* DNA pol I, both DNA pols IA and IB are able to bypass DNA lesions and continue replicating DNA [15]. Therefore, it was suggested that a high degree of fidelity could be due to the presence of 3'-5' PR exonuclease domains, which are generally absent in DNA polymerases, involve in typical translesion synthesis.

1.2. RNA Polymerases of Plant Chloroplasts (PEP and NEP)

As discussed elsewhere, the PEP and NEP are the two enzymes that are involved in the transcription of the chloroplast genome and are extensively studied [5, 16]. Even though both the polymerases are high-fidelity enzymes, they can add a few (10^{-4} to 10^{-5}) mismatched nucleotides during the high-speed transcription processes (2). These mismatched nucleotides may have a null-effect on the growth and survival of an organism or they maybe deleterious, depending upon its location(s) and essentiality of the translated protein(s). Therefore, in order to overcome this problem, it is found that these polymerases do have an intrinsic PR exonuclease, which corrects these mistakes, resulting in error-free transcriptions.

1.3. Roles of PEP and NEP in Plant Chloroplasts

As discussed elsewhere, the chloroplast in higher plants use two different types of RNA polymerases to transcribe all its genes. One is the NEP, which is homologous to the SSU-RNAPs of bacteriophages and mitochondria [2, 17-19] and the other one is the PEP, which is structurally and functionally very similar to the eubacterial MSU-RNAPs. It is interesting to note that the NEP, encoded by the nucleus, is structurally unrelated to PEP, but it belongs to the "SSU-RNAP" protein family of bacteriophages T3, T7, SP6, etc. [5-9]. The NEP mainly involves in the transcription of ~20% of the genes which are essentially non-photosynthetic and housekeeping ones, whereas the PEP involves in transcription of the rest of ~80% of the genes, which are photosynthesis-related and tRNA genes [20,21]. This was evident from the knockout mutants of PEP that showed an albino phenotype and lacked photosynthesis [22,23].

Both NEP and PEP differ in their sensitivity to the antibiotic rifampicin. PEP is sensitive to rifampicin (similar to eubacterial MSU-RNAPs), whereas the NEP is insensitive to rifampicin [5,23,24]. Furthermore, both the enzymes differ in their promoter selections too, (i. e.), NEP and PEP use different promoters for transcriptions. While most of the NEP promoters have the conserved YRTA motif, the PEP promoters resemble the bacterial ' σ 70 promoters type' which are typically characterized by -10 and -35 consensus sequence motifs [25]. However, it should also be noted that a number of PEP promoters lack the -10 or the -35 elements, a few, even both [26,27]. Although chloroplasts possess all the genes for the core subunits of a PEP, but this enzyme can correctly initiate transcription only with the nuclear-encoded σ factor. The NEP transcribes the housekeeping genes as well as the genes of the PEP subunits, viz. *rpoA*, *rpoB*, *rpoC1* and *rpoC2* from two different operons [21] as shown in Figs. 1a and 1b suggesting the primary controls are exercised by the nucleus. In other words, the PEP transcription is controlled by the nucleus by providing the σ factor and transcription of its own genes by the NEP. Therefore, that makes the chloroplast as only a semi-autonomous organelle. (This is true for mitochondria also where NEP transcribes all the mitochondrial genes and hence, it is also a semi-autonomous organelle like chloroplast). Figs. 1a and 1b. show the transcription of PEP genes by NEP and assembly of PEP.

Figure 1a and 1b Schematic diagram showing transcription of PEP genes by NEP and assembly of PEP

Pr, Promoter region; L and S, Large and Small ribosomal protein subunits, *rpoA*, *rpoB*, *rpoC1*, and *rpoC2* are the genes for the different subunits of the PEP.

1.4. RNA Polymerases and Their PR Exonuclease Activities

The error rates of RNA polymerases are very minimal and generally in the range of 10^{-4} to 10^{-5} [2]. However, these errors are corrected during the transcription process itself. Because of this, RNA polymerases have evolved essentially with two different types of PR exonucleases (Table 1). In the MSU-RNAPs of prokaryotes, eukaryotes and chloroplasts, which are involved mainly in mRNA transcriptions, the PR active site is embedded within the polymerase active site itself [4]. However, in other RNA polymerases the PR activity is either found on the same polypeptide as a separate domain (multifunctional enzyme type, MFE) or with a closely associated subunit of the enzyme (multienzyme complex type, MEC). Table 1 shows the different types of PR activities of RNA polymerases known in viruses, prokaryotes, eukaryotes and organelles.

Table 1 PR activities and their localization in viruses, prokaryotes, eukaryotes and organellar RNA polymerases

RNAP/DNAP	Organism	PR active site	Reference
DdRps-MSU-RNAP	Prokaryotes	Intrinsic within the RNAP active site itself	[4]
	Eukaryotes		
DdRps-MSU-RNAPs	All eukaryotic (pols I-III)	Intrinsic within the RNAP active site itself	[4]
DdRps-MSU-RNAPs	Plants (pols IV & V)	Intrinsic within the RNAP active site itself	[4]
RdRps-SSU Types	(+) Strand RNA Viruses (e.g., SARS-CoVs, SARS-related CoVs, Human-CoVs)	DEDD(H)-superfamily# (In the associated ExoN subunit, MEC)	[6]
RdRps-SSU Types	(-) Strand RNA Viruses (e.g., Human influenza Viruses A, B & C)	DEDD(H)- superfamily# (In the PA subunit of the RNA polymerase, MEC)	[7]
	Bacteriophages		
DdDps-SSU Types	T4 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	DEDD(Y) superfamily^ (In the same polypeptide, MFE)	[28]
	Prokaryotes		
DdDps-SSU Types	<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I	DEDD(Y) superfamily^ (In the same polypeptide, MFE)	[1]
	Chloroplasts		
DdRps-SSU Types	DNA pols IA & IB (Plant chloroplasts)	DEDD(Y) superfamily# (In the same polypeptide, MFE)	This work
DdRps-SSU Types	RNAP (NEP) (Plant chloroplasts)	DEDD(H) superfamily# (In the same polypeptide, MFE)	This work

^*E. coli* DNA pol I and pol II types; DNAP, DNA polymerase; RNAP, RNA polymerase;
Similar to the ϵ -subunit of bacterial DNA pols III (replicases)

As the PR activity in the MSU eubacterial type PEP is already discussed in detail by Palanivelu [4], the PR active sites of the NEP and the DNA Pols IA and IB are analyzed and reported in this communication.

2. Material and methods

The protein sequence data of DNA polymerases IA, IB and NEPs from various plant chloroplasts were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. The polymerase and PR active sites are arrived at by the sequence similarity with other DNA and RNA polymerases already reported.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 2 shows the MSA of the DNA polymerases IA of the chloroplasts from various plant sources. (Only the required regions for discussions are shown here). The *A. thaliana* sequence is used as the reference and highlighted in yellow.

The N-terminal regions of ~300 amino acids are not conserved and showed many gaps in the alignment, after that, conservations are observed and a clear demarcation of the PR exonuclease domain is seen (highlighted in red). The PR exonuclease domain contains the typical DEDD(Y)-superfamily active site amino acids and is highlighted in light blue. There is a DxD type of metal-binding site within the PR exonuclease site (highlighted in light green). Again, after ~650 amino acids, a second demarcation in the sequences is seen and that contains the polymerase active site amino acids and are highlighted in green. The polymerase active site region contains the typical active site amino acids highlighted in yellow and a ZBM of -CX₆CX₂CX_nC- type is highlighted in orange. The polymerase region is completely conserved in all pol IA from different plant sources and contains the template-binding -YG- pair, the catalytic amino acid K and the nucleotide discriminating amino acid R at -4 position from the catalytic K. The active site, -R⁴RKAK^{878M}1LNFSIAY^{8G}⁸⁸⁷⁻, is very similar to the well-established active site of *E. coli* DNA pol I, -R⁴RS AK^{758A}1NFGLIY^{8G}- [3] and in close agreement to the active sites of the other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported [1, 2]. The ZBM, within the polymerase region, is suggested to play a structural role. The C-terminal ends in a conserved hexapeptide -NWYSA/GK- in most all of the DNA pol IA, suggesting an important role.

3.1. CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the Chloroplast DNA polymerase IA

tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	DGATPWSTDDAEIAKLQIERQEALRERTPKEMADIGEKNYGKLFQYFPTVPDGLAA	784
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	-PEQTVN-----EV-EKRRGTSVSEETDISAYGTAYTAFGGGKEGREACHA	883
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	-----AAA-----AV-DQASEAQKSKTDVDTSAVGTAYAAFGGGERGKEACHA	708
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	-----DDD-----VE-TSETQKSKTDDTUTSAVGTAYVAFGGGGERGKEACHA	717
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	NS-----CQTEVKPVEIEKSAVGTALAAFPTEEGREACHA	704
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	NP-----SQSEVAREIIDDTAYGTAFSAFTNPPEEGREACHA	714
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	IP-----SQSQTASAQIDKSAYGTAFAAFPTEEGREACHA	751
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	NS-----SQSHVAVSKVDNSAYGTAFAAFPTEEGREACHA	747
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	NP-----SKSHITAVKVDKSAYGTAFAAFPTEEGREACHA	747
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	NT-----SQNQVAPLKIDSSAYGTAYAAFPTEEGREACHA	714
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	NP-----SQSQVAPVTIDKSAYGTAFVAFPTTEEGREACHA	735
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	NP-----SQSQVASVKIDKSAYGTAYAAFPTEEGREACHA	742
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	NP-----SQSQVASVKIDKSAYGTAYAAFPTEEGREACHA	742
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	-GEDISESET-----SE-ASGVLGSTASRNIDTSAYGTAFSAFHNEDEGREACHA	755
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	SPEK-----MTDVTDSAYGTAFAAFEDEKREACHA	832
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	DFETMPHEEN-----R-----RRIVHECANMSDYGTALKAFKKEEGMEACHA	826
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	DFETMPREEN-----R-----RRIIHECANMSDYGTALTAFKKEEGMEACHA	800
tr A0A6J1D925 A0A6J1D925_MOMCH	DSETMPHGEN-----K-----KPVIHESANMSDYGTAFEFASKEEGREACHA	797
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	DSETVSHVEN-----K-----KHIIHESANMSDYGTALKAFGSSKEEGREACHA	792
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	DSETMTDED-----L-----ESKELSVVENENESHVGNLRRFQTPEEGIEACHA	670
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	DYKAAATDVSE-----KE-----EPEEPKAVDSSAYGTAFTAFADSKLEEEGREACHA	817

tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	VDSLIDASAIDTLLSNFIIPLQSDDISKPDASGVYRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	844
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	IAALCEVCSIDSLVSNFILPLOGSHILGKN---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	939
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	IASLCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNVSGKD---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	764
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	IASLCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNVSGKD---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	773
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	IASLCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGCNILGKD---HRIHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	760
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	IAALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNVSGRN---GRIHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	770
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGHNSGKD---NRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	807
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGHNSGKD---NRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	803
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGHNSGKD---NRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	803
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGNISGKD---LRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	770
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGHNSGKD---LRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	791
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGHNSGKD---LRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	798
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	IAALCEVCSINSLISNFILPLOGHNSGKD---LRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	798
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	IAALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNVSGKD---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	811
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	IASLCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNVSGKS---ERVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	888
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	IAALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNISGKN---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	882
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	ISALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNISGKN---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	856
tr A0A6J1D925 A0A6J1D925_MOMCH	IAALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNISGKN---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	853
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	IAALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNISGKN---GRIHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	848
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	ISSLCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNISGKS---GRVHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	726
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	IAALCEVCSIDSLISNFILPLOGSNISGKN---GRIHCSLNINTETGRLSARRPNLQNO	873

tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	PALEKDRYRVRKAFTADRKA ¹ SKTLIVADYGOLELRILAHMANCQSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	904
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ² ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	997
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	PALEKDRYKIRKAFTAA--P ³ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLAGCKSMMAQAFKAGGDFHSRT	822
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	PALEKDRYKIRKAFTAA--P ⁴ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLAGCKSMMAQAFKAGGDFHSRT	831
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ⁵ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	818
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ⁶ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLAGCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	828
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	PALEKDRYKIRKAFTAA--P ⁷ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	865
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ⁸ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMMAQAFKAGGDFHSRT	861
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ⁹ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	861
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁰ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	861
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹¹ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	828
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹² ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	849
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹³ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	856
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁴ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	856
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁵ ENSLVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	869
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁶ ENSLVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	946
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁷ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	940
tr A0A6J1D925 A0A6J1D925_MOMCH	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁸ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	914
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ¹⁹ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	911
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ²⁰ ENSLIVADYGOLELRVLAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	906
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	PALEKDRYKIRQAFTAA--P ²¹ ENSLIVADYGOLELRILAHLANCKSMLEAFKAGGDFHSRT	784

tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	ALGYMDHIQDAIAGKNCLEWDGVAEDGSYTPPPVPLKLDYGA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	964
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	AMNMYPHIRKAVEQKQVLEWHWPQTG---EVKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	1054
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	AMNMYPHIRKAVDNGEVLLEWHWPQTG---QDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	879
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	AMNMYPHVREAVENGQVILEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	888
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	AMNMYPYICDAVNEKQVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	875
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	AMNMYPYIREAVEKNQVLEWHWPQTG---EEKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	885
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	AMNMYPYIREAVDKKEVLEWHWPQTG---EEKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	922
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	AMNMYPYIREAVEKKEVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	918
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	AMNMYPYIROAVEKKEVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	918
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	AMNMYPFIREAVEKKEVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	885
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	AMNMYPYIREAVEKQVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	906
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	AMNMYPHIREAVEKKEVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	913
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	AMNMYPHIREAVEKKEVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	913
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	AMNMYQHIREAVEKKEVLEWHWPQTG---DDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	926
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	AMNMYSHIREAVEKRVLEWHWPQTG---QEKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	1003
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	AMNMYPHIRKAVEEGSVLEWDPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	997
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	AMNMYPHIRKAVEEGSVLEWDPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	971
tr A0A6J1D9Z5 A0A6J1D9Z5_MOMCH	AMNMYPHIRNAVEKGSVLEWDPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	968
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	AMNMYPHIRKAVEEGSVLEWDPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	963
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	AVNMYPHIREAIEKRVLEWHWPQTG---EDKPPVPLLKDAFA	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	841
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	AMNMYPHIREAIEKRVLEWHWPQTG---EEKPPVPLLKDAFG	ERRRKYLNFSIAFGK	988
	:..* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.*		

		Pol ← → CTD	
tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	KSGNKAAKAHALRAAINTPI-----	QGSAADVATAAMLRI TADERLREMGW	1070
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	DHASNAQCGHIERAAINTPV-----		1133
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	--QSRQKNHIQRAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIITNQRKLKELGW	983
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	--KSRQKNHIQRAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISINQQLKELGW	992
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	DQATNYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQIWNNEQLKDLGW	981
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	ARATPSQKNHIERAAINTPVQLFSDDFLIYKMG	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISKNRKLKELGW	1005
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	GQANKYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISNNKQLKELGW	1028
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	AQANTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQISNNKQLKELGW	1024
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	AQANTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQISNNKQLKELGW	1024
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	AQANTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQISNNKQLKELGW	991
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	AQANTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQISNNKQLKELGW	1012
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	AQANTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQISNNKQLKELGW	1019
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	AQANTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQISNNKQLKELGW	1019
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	AHASRAHRNHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLRIITNNKQLEDLGW	1032
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	AQCTYQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMLQIKLNEQLKELGW	1109
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	KQVTRAQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISKNRRLRELGW	1103
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	KQVTRAQKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISKNRRLRELGW	1077
tr A0A6J1D9Z5 A0A6J1D9Z5_MOMCH	KHATRAQRGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISNNSGLRELGW	1074
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	KHATRAKGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISKNRRLRELGW	1069
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	TDASSSLRGHVERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISKNRRLRELGW	947
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	RHATRSQRGHIERAAINTPV-----	QGSAADVAMCAMEIISNETLRELGW	1094
	* * * * * :		

tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPKETAETIAQAVVCEMRS PFGDAGGDLRVELSVDSKYADTWYDA		1129
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	----QVHDEVILEGPNESAEEARAIVVKCMSKPFY--GTNFKVLDLSDAKCAQNNWYAA		1186
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	RLLL-QIHDEVILEGPMESAELAKDIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILSVLDLSDAKCAQNNWYAA		1040
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	RLLL-QIHDEVILEGPIESAELAKDIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILSVLDLSDAKCAQNNWYAA		1049
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYAG		1038
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1062
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1085
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFY--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1081
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	RLLLQVHDEVILEGPTESAIEFAKIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1082
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYAG		1048
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSG		1069
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSG		1076
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	RLLL-QVLESTINSIHSFA-----LSWE--G-----DWGNK		1047
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYAA		1090
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYAA		1167
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1160
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1134
tr A0A6J1D9Z5 A0A6J1D9Z5_MOMCH	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1131
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1126
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1004
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	RLLL-QVHDEVILEGPTESAIEVAIVVDCMSKPFN--GKNILKVDLSDAKCAQNNWYSA		1151
	:..* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.* :.*.*		

//End of DNA pol IA sequences		
tr A0A8T2W5E6 A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO	K	1130
tr A0A1U8QBT1 A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU	K	1187
tr A0A6J0P749 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA	K	1041
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	K	1050
tr A0A6P4CP16 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU	K	1039
tr A0A834U2N1 A0A834U2N1_9FABA	K	1063
tr A0A6P4DWB3 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU	K	1086
tr A0A1S2XND1 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR	K	1082
tr A0A8B8MN50 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR	K	1083
tr A0A1S3UFS3 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR	K	1049
tr A0A371FAB7 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR	K	1070
tr A0A445LVJ8 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO	K	1077
tr A0A445LVL1 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO	H	1048
tr A0A8B8Q8R9 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT	K	1091
tr A0A6P5WN92 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI	K	1168
tr A0A6J1EVX1 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO	K	1161
tr A0A6J1J7E3 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA	K	1135
tr A0A6J1D9Z5 A0A6J1D9Z5_MOMCH	K	1132
tr A0A6J1IIP1 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA	K	1127
tr A0A4U5R370 A0A4U5R370_POPAL	K	1005
tr A0A6P4ALP7 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ	K	1152
	:	

A0A8T2W5E6_9CHLO, *Chlorella desiccata*
 A0A6J0P749_RAPSA, *Raphanus sativus*
 A0A6P4CP16_ARADU, *Arachis duranensis*
 A0A6P4DWB3_ARADU, *Arachis duranensis*
 A0A8B8MN50_ABRPR, *Abrus precatorius*
 A0A371FAB7_MUCPR, *Mucuna pruriens*
 A0A445LVL1_GLYSO, *Glycine soja*
 A0A6P5WN92_DURZI, *Durio zibethinus*
 A0A6J1J7E3_CUCMA, *Cucurbita maxima*
 A0A6J1IIP1_CUCMA, *Cucurbita maxima*
 A0A6P4ALP7_ZIZJJ, *Ziziphus jujube*

A0A1U8QBT1_NELNU, *Nelumbo nucifera*
F4I6M1|POLIA_ARATH, *Arabidopsis thaliana*
 A0A834U2N1_9FABA, *Senna tora*
 A0A1S2XND1_CICAR, *Cicer arietinum*
 A0A1S3UFS3_VIGRR, *Vigna radiata*
 A0A445LVJ8_GLYSO, *Glycine soja*
 A0A8B8Q8R9_9MYRT, *Rhodamnia argentea*
 A0A6J1EVX1_CUCMO, *Cucurbita moschata*
 A0A6J1D9Z5_MOMCH, *Momordica charantia*
 A0A4U5R370_POPAL, *Populus alba*

Figure 2 MSA of DNA polymerase IA of various plant chloroplasts

Figure 3 shows the MSA of the DNA polymerase 1B of the chloroplasts from various plant sources. (Only the required regions for discussions are shown here). The *A. thaliana* sequence is used as the reference and highlighted. The N-terminal region of ~250 amino acids is not conserved and shows many gaps in the alignment as in pol IA and, after that, conservations are observed and a clear demarcation of the PR exonuclease domain is seen (highlighted in red) as in pol IA. The PR exonuclease domain contains the typical DEDD(Y)-superfamily active site amino acids and are highlighted in light blue. There is a DxD type of metal-binding site within the PR exonuclease site in many of them (highlighted in light green). The polymerase active site region is highlighted in green. The polymerase active site region contains the typical active site amino acids highlighted in yellow and a ZBM of -CX₆CX₂C_nC- type is highlighted in orange and is identical to the DNA pol IA. The polymerase region is completely conserved in all and contains the template-binding -YG- pair, the catalytic amino acid K and the nucleotide discriminating amino acid R at -4 position from the catalytic K. The active site, -R⁴RKAK⁸⁶²M¹LNFSIAY^{8G}⁷¹-, is identical to DNA pol IA (-R⁴RKAKM¹LNFSIAY^{8G}-) and is very similar to the well-established active site of *E. coli* DNA pol I, -R⁴RSAK⁷⁵⁸A¹INFLGIY^{8G}- [3]. The polymerase active sites from DNA pol IA and IB are in close agreement with the active sites of the other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported [1, 2]. The ZBM, in the polymerase region, is suggested to play a structural role. The C-terminal ends in a conserved hexapeptide -NWYTAK- in all, suggesting an important role.

3.2. CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the Chloroplast DNA Polymerase IB

tr A0A1S3YPG4 A0A1S3YPG4_TOBAC	EKNAIQ---SMATDVVNGTKTRIVSDEGSGVSVLSRRLRGAMYDKVHV	DNLSAAKEIV	375
tr A0A1U7VL87 A0A1U7VL87_NICSY	EKNAIQ---SMETDVVNGTKTRIVSDEGTGVSQVLSRRLRGAMYDKVHV	DNLSAAKEVV	375
tr A0A0V0J0J1 A0A0V0J0J1_SOLCH	EKNAIK---SVATDFVNGTETKIVSDEGTGLGQITLRLRGAMYDKVHV	DNLSAAKEVV	325
tr A0A1U8FC39 A0A1U8FC39_CAPAN	EKNTIQ---SVATTVVNGTETKIVSDEGTGLGQVTLRLRGVMEKVVHV	DNLSAAKEVV	339
tr A0A6I9UH37 A0A6I9UH37_SESIN	K-K--EAKPAAKKTVLSDTVSEPLSEKITASGGTELHERLSQVYDITLVV	DSIPAAQGVV	311
tr A0A8S0VP65 A0A8S0VP65_OLEEU	VIDEIKNGAADRKCIADIARTQIE-TITHESKNI FERLRTVYDKVLVV	DSISVAREVV	331
tr A0A6J0P5F8 A0A6J0P5F8_RAPSA	DVRGRQRPLVASFDSARNESTVTISKVGKRTDLSRVANLTKIYNKVRVV	DNVSTAKEIV	243
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	-VTLKPLNSDTTLDNASYKKTATISKVEKCTNLSQVRANLKKIYNKVRVV	DNVSSAKETV	257
tr A0A6J1ALP4 A0A6J1ALP4_9ROSI	NQDTGHTNPNVTRRRDRANE SGVASTEEDNVSVSQEDISKRLARIYDQVLVV	DNVSVAREVV	396
tr A0A1U8MKL7 A0A1U8MKL7_GOSHI	IQDRGHMDPNVTRRRDQANENGVASSEENLPVYRNDIHKQLAKIYDQVLVV	DNISVAREVV	374
tr A0A0B0MAF8 A0A0B0MAF8_GOSAR	IQYRRHMDPNATRRDQANENGVASSEENLPVYRNDIHKQLAKIYNQVLVV	DNISVAREVV	401
tr A0A1U8KJG2 A0A1U8KJG2_GOSHI	IQYRGHMDPNATRRDQANENGVASSEENLPVYRNDIHKQLAKIYNQVLVV	DNISVAREVV	401
tr A0A6J1FW48 A0A6J1FW48_CUCMO	NGLKRGAAVEEFSKMTINGGGTKITEAPATSHKPKDIKERLNGVYDVLVV	DSIQAAKEVV	352
tr A0A6P8EEL6 A0A6P8EEL6_PUNGR	VGTS-VLVSEPFPEDEAVVAFGVDAADKASNTSEDVVRKLRGIYEEVIVV	DNISMAREIV	404
tr A0A1S2Y7M1 A0A1S2Y7M1_CICAR	NGNH-SLAT-TAKDKTQAKSAVA---MIRSDEQLKLRDLRCSIYEDILVV	NNLSHAEVA	321
tr A0A1S3VL91 A0A1S3VL91_VIGRR	EDKC-NLET-IAKYEANAT---SVKKAR-SSEQLKLRGRRLCSIYEDILVV	NNISLAEVA	285
tr A0A371ED47 A0A371ED47_MUCPR	NGDC-DMDT-TAKDATNATNATSVKKAR-STEQSKLRDLRCSIYEDILVV	NNISLAEVA	262
tr A0A8B8KCR7 A0A8B8KCR7_ABRPR	NGNH-SSGT-TAKDATNAT---SVKKTRSRREEQSKLCDRLCSIYEDVLVV	NDISLAEKVA	301

→ Exo

: . * : * : : * : : : * : .

//End of DNA pol IB sequences			
tr A0A1S3YPG4 A0A1S3YPG4_TOBAC	CAKNWYSAK		1152
tr A0A1U7VL87 A0A1U7VL87_NICSY	CAKNWYSAK		1152
tr A0A0V0J0J1 A0A0V0J0J1_SOLCH	CAKNWYSAK		1102
tr A0A1U8FC39 A0A1U8FC39_CAPAN	CAKNWYAAK		1116
tr A0A6I9UH37 A0A6I9UH37_SESIN	CAQNWYSAK		1079
tr A0A8S0VP65 A0A8S0VP65_OLEEU	-----		1058
tr A0A6J0P5F8 A0A6J0P5F8_RAPSA	CAQNWYAAK		1018
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	CAQNWYAGK		1034
tr A0A6J1ALP4 A0A6J1ALP4_9ROSI	CAQNWYAAK		1159
tr A0A1U8MKL7 A0A1U8MKL7_GOSHI	CAQNWYAAK		1136
tr A0A0B0MAF8 A0A0B0MAF8_GOSAR	CAQNWYAAK		1163
tr A0A1U8KJG2 A0A1U8KJG2_GOSHI	CAQNWYAAK		1163
tr A0A6J1FW48 A0A6J1FW48_CUCMO	CARNWYSAK		1127
tr A0A6P8EE16 A0A6P8EE16_PUNGR	CAQNWYAAK		1179
tr A0A1S2Y7M1 A0A1S2Y7M1_CICAR	CAQNWYAAK		1087
tr A0A1S3VL91 A0A1S3VL91_VIGRR	CAQNWYAAK		1052
tr A0A371ED47 A0A371ED47_MUCPR	CAQNWYAAK		1029
tr A0A8B8KCR7 A0A8B8KCR7_ABRPR	CACNWYAK		1068

A0A1S3YPG4_TOBAC, <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	A0A1U7VL87_NICSY, <i>Nicotiana sylvestris</i>
A0A0V0J0J1_SOLCH, <i>Solanum chacoense</i>	A0A1U8FC39_CAPAN, <i>Capsicum annuum</i>
A0A6I9UH37_SESIN, <i>Sesamum indicum</i>	A0A8S0VP65_OLEEU, <i>Olea europaea</i>
A0A0B0MAF8_GOSAR, <i>Gossypium arboreum</i>	A0A6J0P5F8_RAPSA, <i>Raphanus sativus</i>
Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH, <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	A0A6J1ALP4_9ROSI, <i>Herrania umbratica</i>
A0A1U8MKL7_GOSHI, <i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	A0A1U8KJG2_GOSHI, <i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>
A0A6J1FW48_CUCMO, <i>Cucurbita moschata</i>	A0A6P8EE16_PUNGR, <i>Punica granatum</i>
A0A1S2Y7M1_CICAR, <i>Cicer arietinum</i>	A0A1S3VL91_VIGRR, <i>Vigna radiate</i>

Figure 3 MSA of DNA polymerase IB from various plant chloroplasts

All three polymerases, viz. *E. coli* DNA pol I, DNA pol IA and IB from *A. thaliana* chloroplast are subjected to Mix and Match MSA analysis to find out the identities, similarities and conservation(s) between them. Figure 4 shows the ‘Mix and Match’ MSA of all three DNA pols. (only the required regions for discussions are shown). The *E. coli* DNA pol I is used as the reference and is highlighted in yellow. Interestingly, all three show identical polymerase and PR exonuclease catalytic core amino acids, suggesting their close evolutionary relatedness. However, in contrast to the *E. coli* DNA pol I, two possible ZBMs (highlighted in orange) are found in both the active site regions of *A. thaliana*’s DNA pol IA and IB (highlighted in orange) (Fig. 4), suggesting structural roles.

3.3. CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of *E. coli* DNA pol I, and DNA pols IA and IB from *A. thaliana* chloroplasts

sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	AWIAK---LEKAPVFAFDTEVSDSLDNISANLV---GLSFAIEPGVAAYIPV--AHDYLD	391
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	DTVAKLVNQFRNHVHSDDTEVSGIEVKEETPVDHGELTFSIYGGPEADFGNGKSCIIWVD	336
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	ETVALLMNQYRNLVHVAQDTEVSRIDVKTETPVDHGEMICFSIYGGSEADFGDGKSCIIWVD	314
	:* : *..***. . : . * : **.* * * : : **	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	APDQISRERALELLKPLLEDEKALKVGNLKYDRGILANYGIELRGIAFDTMLESYILNS	451
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	VLGE-NGREVLAEFKPYFEDSFKRKVWHNYSHDSHIIRNHGIEISGFHADTMHMARLWDS	395
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	VLGE-NGRDILAEFKPFEDSSIKKVVWHNYSFDNHIIRNYGIKLSGFHGDTHMARLWDS	373
	. . : . . * : ** : ** . ** : * . * * : * : * : * : * : * : * : *	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	FNQIALEE---GRVAAEDADVTL-----QLHLKMWPDQ---KHKGPLNVFENIEM	531
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	VEELQREDREAWISYSAIDAIISTLKLYESMKTQLMDWHLDGKPV LGRTMLDFYHEFWR	515
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	VKELQMEDREAWISYSAIDSIISTLKLYESMKTQLQAKKWFLDGKLI SKKNMFDYQYEWQ	493
	.. : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : * : *	

sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	L-----EYR-----GLAKLKSTYTD-KLPL	646
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	SETQKSKTDEDETDTSAYGTAYVAFGGGGERGKEA CH AIASL CE VCSIDSLISNFIPLPQGS	741
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	VETQHVNTSVESDTSAYGTAFDAFGGSGKEA CH AI AA L CE VCSIDSLISNFIPLPQGS	725
	: : : : * * * :	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	MINPKTGRVHTSYHQAVTATGRLSSTDPNLQNI PVR NEEGRRIR QAF IAPEDYVIVS ADY	706
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	NVSGKDGRVH SL N-INTETGRLSARREN LQ NPAL EK D R YKIRKAFV AS PGNTLV VADY	800
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	NVSGKDGRVH SL N-INTETGRLSARREN LQ NPAL EK D R YKIR QAF I AS PGNSLIV ADY	784
	: . * * * * * * : * * * * * : * * * * * * * : : : : * * * * * * * : : : * * * * * * * :	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	-----TVTSE QR RS AK AIN FGL I Y GM S AFGLAR Q LNI PR KEA Q K Y MDLY F ERY P GVLE	800
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	PPVPLLKDAFGSE RR KA K MLN F SI A Y G K TAVGLSRD W KVST K EA Q ET V DL W Y N D R Q E VR K	920
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	PPVPLLKDAF AS E RR KA K MLN F SI A Y G K TAIGLSRD W KV S RE A Q D T V N L W Y N D R Q E V R K	904
	: . . . * * * * * : * * * * * : * * * * * * * : : * * * * * * * : : * * * * * * * :	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	YMER T RA Q AK E Q G Y V ET L D G RR L Y L P D IK S NGARR A A E RA I NA M Q G TA A D I IK R AM	860
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	W Q EM R KK E A I ED G Y V LT L GR S RR F P A SK S R-- A QR N H I Q R A I NT P V Q G S A A D V AM C AM	978
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	W Q EL R KK E A I Q K Y V LT L GR A R K F P E Y R S R-- A Q R N H I E R A IN T P V Q G S A A D V A M C AM	962
	: * : : * : . * * * * * * * * : * : * * : : * * * * * * * : * * * * * * * : * * * * * * * :	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	IAVD A W L Q A E Q PR V RM I M Q V H DE L V F EV H K D D V DA V AK--- Q I H Q L M E N C T R L D V P LL V	916
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	LE I S I N Q L K K L G W R L L L Q I H D E V I L E G P I E S A E I A K D I V D C M S K P F N G R N I L S V D L S V	1038
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	LE I S I N Q R L K E L G W K L L L Q V H D E V I L E G P S E S A E N A K D I V V N C M S E P F N G K N I L S V D L S V	1022
	: : . : : : : * * * * * : * * * * * : : : : : : * * * * * : : : : : * * * * * :	
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	EV G S G E N W D Q A H	928
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	DA K CA Q N W Y A AK	1050
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	DA K CA Q N W Y A G K	1034
	: . . . * * * * * :	

Figure 4 Mix and Match MSA of the *E. coli* DNA pol I, and the chloroplast DNA pols IA and IB from *A. thaliana*

3.4. PR exonuclease Active Site Structures of the DNA Polymerases IA and IB

Figure 5 shows the organization of the different domains on the DNA polymerases IA and IB from *A. thaliana* chloroplasts. The NTD domain of the polymerases is not conserved whereas the other four domains are highly conserved in both. A typical ZBM precedes the Pol domain and distinguishes these polymerases from the *E. coli* DNA pol I.

NTD, N-terminal domain; DEDD, PR exonuclease domain; ZBM, zinc-binding motif; Pol, polymerase domain; CTD, C-terminal domain.

Figure 5 A schematic diagramme showing the domain structure of the DNA polymerases IA and IB from plant chloroplasts (numbering from *A. thaliana*)

Based on the above data, amino acids at active sites of PR exonucleases of chloroplast DNA polymerases IA and IB are proposed (Fig. 6). The exonuclease active site is found to be very similar to the established active site of the *E. coli* DNA pol I and follows DEDD-superfamily (Fig. 4). In all three enzymes, the active site Tyr accepts the proton from the metal-bound water molecule to initiate catalysis which is followed by the formation of a highly reactive Zn-hydroxyl free radical, leading to the removal of a misincorporated nucleotide. Thus, the 3'→5' exonuclease↔polymerase activities switch between excision and incorporation modes without dissociation of the enzyme-substrate complex [29].

A. Thaliana DNA pol IA -D²⁹⁴TE²⁹⁶-----FD³⁶⁸S-----SY⁴⁷⁰S→3 aa→D⁴⁷⁴AI-

A. Thaliana DNA pol IB -D²⁷²TE²⁷⁴-----FD³⁴⁶N-----SY⁴⁴⁸S→3 aa→D⁴⁵²SI-

E. coli DNA pol I -D³⁵⁵TE³⁵⁷-----YD⁴²⁴R-----RY⁴⁹⁷A→3 aa→D⁵⁰¹AD-

(Active site amino acids highlighted in dark blue are confirmed by site-directed mutagenesis (SDM) experiments analysis).

Figure 6 Proposed amino acids at the PR exonuclease active sites of the DNA polymerases IA and IB of plant chloroplasts. (the amino acid numberings are from the *A. thaliana*)

3.5. Active site Structures of the Polymerases of DNA Polymerases IA and IB

Based on the above data, amino acids at active sites of the DNA polymerase IA and IB of chloroplasts are proposed (Fig. 7). Interestingly, the polymerase active site amino acids are found to be identical to the well-established active site amino acids of the *E. coli* DNA pol I (Fig. 4). In all three enzymes, the active site K abstracts the proton from the 3'-OH of the growing primer to initiate catalysis, which is followed by a nucleophilic-electrophilic attack with the subsequent addition of the incoming base to the growing primer. For a detailed mechanism, see Palanivelu [30].

Figure 7 Proposed amino acids at the active sites of the DNA polymerases IA and IB of the plant chloroplasts. (the amino acid numberings are from the *A. thaliana*)

Figure 8 shows the MSA of the NEPs from the chloroplasts of various plant sources. (Only the required regions for discussions are shown here). The *A. thaliana* sequence is used as the reference and highlighted in yellow. The N-terminal region up to 400-500 amino acids is not conserved and shows many gaps in the alignment and, after that, conservations are observed and a clear demarcation of the PR exonuclease domain is also seen (highlighted in red). The PR exonuclease domain contains the typical DEDD(H) superfamily active site amino acids and is highlighted in light blue. A DxD type of metal-binding site within the PR exonuclease site is also found (highlighted in light green). Again, after ~750 amino acids a second demarcation in the sequences is observed and that contains the polymerase active site

region and highlighted in green. The polymerase region contains the typical active site amino acids highlighted in yellow and a DxD type metal-binding motif (highlighted in dark green). The polymerase region is completely conserved in all and contains the template-binding -YG- pair, the catalytic amino acid K and the nucleotide discriminating amino acid R at -4 position from the catalytic K. The active site -R⁴KLVKQ¹TVMTSVY⁸G-, is very similar to the active site of *E. coli* DNA pol I, -R⁴RSAK⁷⁵⁸A¹INFLGIY⁸G- [3] and in close agreement to the active sites of the other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported [1,2]. The C-terminal end is remarkably conserved and ends in the tetrapeptide -YFFN- suggesting an important role. However, the ZBM is not located in the RNA polymerase NEP, as in chloroplast DNA pols IA and IB.

3.6. CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of NEPs from the Chloroplasts of Various Plant Sources

tr A0A251TQF3 A0A251TQF3 HELAN	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	625
tr A0A803MFE3 A0A803MFE3 CHEQI	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLQWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	626
tr A0A565CQ27 A0A565CQ27 9BRAS	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	638
tr V4L7M1 V4L7M1 EUTSA	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLYWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	632
tr R0HH96 R0HH96 9BRAS	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	630
sp O24600 RPO33 ARATH	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	629
tr D7LGR7 D7LGR7 ARALL	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	629
tr A0A078G6J8 A0A078G6J8 BRANA	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLYWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	615
tr A0A6J0K1N7 A0A6J0K1N7 RAPSA	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLYWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	621
tr A0A397Y433 A0A397Y433 BRACM	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGRTLEFAEGRPLGKESGLYWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	618
sp Q8L6J1 RPO3B TOBAC	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLSLYAGGVEKLSYDAR	616
tr A0A1U8H8N9 A0A1U8H8N9 CAPAN	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFSEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDAR	617
tr A0A803QAW0 A0A803QAW0 CANSI	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIQLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	618
tr A0A5N6RVV2 A0A5N6RVV2 9ROSI	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	619
tr A0A6J1I1C4 A0A6J1I1C4 CUCMA	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDAR	618
tr A0A6J1E061 A0A6J1E061 MOMCH	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDAR	610
tr A0A0A0LH38 A0A0A0LH38 CUCSA	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDAR	614
tr A0A1S3BU26 A0A1S3BU26 CUCME	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDAR	614
tr A0A835UM73 A0A835UM73 VANPL	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	664
tr A0A4S8JC56 A0A4S8JC56 MUSBA	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	695
tr A0A445DB12 A0A445DB12 ARAHY	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	659
tr A0A0E0QNFS A0A0E0QNFS ORYRU	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	622
tr A0A6P6BHY6 A0A6P6BHY6 DURZ1	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	635
tr A0A5E4F8X8 A0A5E4F8X8 FRUDU	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFSEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	645
tr IM5XKH1 IM5XKH1 PRUPE	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFSEGRPLGKESGLRMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	645
tr A0A2C9WDN1 A0A2C9WDN1 MANES	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLQWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	669
tr A0A6P6TN25 A0A6P6TN25 COFAR	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGVLEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	679
tr A0A1U72W01 A0A1U72W01 NELNU	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLQWLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSYDGR	670
tr D7SML3 D7SML3 VITVI	FRGRAYPMHPEFLNLS	SL	LCRGILEFAEGRPLGKESGLHMLKIHLANLYAGGVEKLSHDDR	674

	Exo ←	→ Pol			
tr A0A251TQF3 A0A251TQF3 HELAN	-----	SYPNALLARLLIGQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	778
tr A0A803MFE3 A0A803MFE3 CHEQI	-----	TYPSALLAKVLDVQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	779
tr A0A565CQ27 A0A565CQ27 9BRAS	-----	SNPTAALAKIVINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	791
tr V4L7M1 V4L7M1 EUTSA	-----	SNPTAALAKILINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	785
tr R0HH96 R0HH96 9BRAS	-----	SNPTAALAKILITQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	783
sp O24600 RPO33 ARATH	-----	SNPTAALAKILITQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	785
tr D7LGR7 D7LGR7 ARALL	-----	SNPTAALAKILITQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	782
tr A0A078G6J8 A0A078G6J8 BRANA	-----	SNPTAALAKILINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	768
tr A0A6J0K1N7 A0A6J0K1N7 RAPSA	-----	SNPTAALAKILINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	774
tr A0A397Y433 A0A397Y433 BRACM	-----	SNPTAALAKILINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	771
sp Q8L6J1 RPO3B TOBAC	-----	IDPNALLAKLLIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	769
tr A0A1U8H8N9 A0A1U8H8N9 CAPAN	-----	ADPNALLAKLLIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	770
tr A0A803QAW0 A0A803QAW0 CANSI	-----	RHPCASLAKILIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	771
tr A0A5N6RVV2 A0A5N6RVV2 9ROSI	-----	TNPHAVLAKILIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	772
tr A0A6J1I1C4 A0A6J1I1C4 CUCMA	-----	ANPNALLAKILIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	771
tr A0A6J1E061 A0A6J1E061 MOMCH	-----	TNPNALLAKILIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	763
tr A0A0A0LH38 A0A0A0LH38 CUCSA	-----	TNPNASLAKLLIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	767
tr A0A1S3BU26 A0A1S3BU26 CUCME	-----	TNPNASLAKLLIDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	767
tr A0A835UM73 A0A835UM73 VANPL	YDGSQRIIPGLKEILLAEIKKL	KVEQRKSVKMFYTLKQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	843
tr A0A4S8JC56 A0A4S8JC56 MUSBA	-----	VNRDALRARLLVDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	848
tr A0A445DB12 A0A445DB12 ARAHY	-----	IFPPALHARLLVQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	812
tr A0A0E0QNFS A0A0E0QNFS ORYRU	-----	TDFPAAARALLLDQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	775
tr A0A6P6BHY6 A0A6P6BHY6 DURZ1	-----	ANPNALHARLLINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	788
tr A0A5E4F8X8 A0A5E4F8X8 FRUDU	-----	TNPNALHARLLINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	798
tr IM5XKH1 IM5XKH1 PRUPE	-----	TNPNALHARLLINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	798
tr A0A2C9WDN1 A0A2C9WDN1 MANES	-----	VFPDALHARTLINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	822
tr A0A6P6TN25 A0A6P6TN25 COFAR	-----	VFPDALRARVLVQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	832
tr A0A1U72W01 A0A1U72W01 NELNU	-----	THPNAMHARILINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	823
tr D7SML3 D7SML3 VITVI	-----	IFPDALRARILINQVNR	KLK	QVMTSVYGVTFVGAR	827

		Pol ←	CTD ↑				
tr A0A251TQF3 A0A251TQF3 HELAN	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	KMNVLREKFFVELYRTPILE	N	950
tr A0A803MFE3 A0A803MFE3 CHEQI	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	KMNQILREKFFVELYSMPILE	N	951
tr A0A565CQ27 A0A565CQ27 9BRAS	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYNIPILE	D	963
tr V4L7M1 V4L7M1 EUTSA	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYNIPILE	D	957
tr R0HH96 R0HH96 9BRAS	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYNIPILE	D	955
sp O24600 RPO33 ARATH	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYNIPILE	D	957
tr D7LGR7 D7LGR7 ARALL	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYNIPILE	D	954
tr A0A078G6J8 A0A078G6J8 BRANA	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYSSPILE	D	940
tr A0A6J0K1N7 A0A6J0K1N7 RAPSA	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYSTPILE	D	946
tr A0A397Y433 A0A397Y433 BRACM	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACREAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYSTPILE	D	943
sp Q8L6J1 RPO3B TOBAC	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYSLPILE	D	941
tr A0A1U8H8N9 A0A1U8H8N9 CAPAN	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYSSMPILE	D	942
tr A0A803QAW0 A0A803QAW0 CANSI	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNQILRQFFVELYSMPILE	N	943
tr A0A5N6RVV2 A0A5N6RVV2 9ROSI	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	KMNQILRDKFFVELYSKPILE	N	944
tr A0A6J1I1C4 A0A6J1I1C4 CUCMA	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTALACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNLIREKFFVELYNIPILE	T	943
tr A0A6J1E061 A0A6J1E061 MOMCH	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTALACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNVIIRETFFVELYNIPILE	S	935
tr A0A0A0LH38 A0A0A0LH38 CUCSA	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTALACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNLIREKFFVELYSMPILE	S	939
tr A0A1S3BU26 A0A1S3BU26 CUCME	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTALACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNLIREKFFVELYSMPILE	S	939
tr A0A835UM73 A0A835UM73 VANPL	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNVIIREKFFVELYSMPILE	S	939
tr A0A4S8JC56 A0A4S8JC56 MUSBA	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACRDAGLRFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNVIIREKFFVELYSMPILE	S	939
tr A0A445DB12 A0A445DB12 ARAHY	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	984
tr A0A0E0QNFS A0A0E0QNFS ORYRU	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	947
tr A0A6P6BHY6 A0A6P6BHY6 DURZ1	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	960
tr A0A5E4F8X8 A0A5E4F8X8 FRUDU	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	970
tr IM5XKH1 IM5XKH1 PRUPE	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	970
tr A0A2C9WDN1 A0A2C9WDN1 MANES	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	S	994
tr A0A6P6TN25 A0A6P6TN25 COFAR	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	1004
tr A0A1U72W01 A0A1U72W01 NELNU	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	995
tr D7SML3 D7SML3 VITVI	FVHSLDGTTHMMMTAVACKKAGLNFAGV	YDSD	YVWTHACD	QVNR	DMNRIREKFFVELYETPILE	N	999

//End of NEP sequences		
tr A0A251TQF3 A0A251TQF3_HELAN	LLSFQTTYPGLEFPPLPPRGDFDLNEVLKSE	YFFN 986
tr A0A803MFE3 A0A803MFE3_CHEQI	LLSQFQESYPESTFPPLPERGNFELEKVLSE	YFFN 987
tr A0A565CQ27 A0A565CQ27_9BRAS	LLSQFQESYPNLEFPFVPPQGRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 999
tr V4L7M1 V4L7M1_EUTSA	LLSQFQESYPNLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 993
tr R0HH96 R0HH96_9BRAS	LLSQFQESYPNLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 991
sp O24600 RPOT3_ARATH	LLSQFQESYPNLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 993
tr D7LGR7 D7LGR7_ARALL	LLSQFQESYPNLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 990
tr A0A078G6J8 A0A078G6J8_BRANA	LLSQFQESYPTLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 976
tr A0A6J0K1N7 A0A6J0K1N7_RAPSA	LLSQFQESYPNLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSH	YFFN 982
tr A0A397Y433 A0A397Y433_BRACM	LLSQFQESYPNLVFPFVPPKRGDFDLKEVLKSC	YFFN 979
sp Q8L6J1 RPO3B_TOBAC	LLENFQKSYPALTFPPLPKRGDFNLREVLESE	YFFN 977
tr A0A1U8H8N9 A0A1U8H8N9_CAPAN	LLSQFQESYPALTFPPLPKRGDFDLREVLESE	YFFN 978
tr A0A803QAW0 A0A803QAW0_CANSA	LLENFQTSYPELEFPPIPERGSFNLQEVLSN	YFFN 979
tr A0A5N6RVV2 A0A5N6RVV2_9ROSI	LLVVSFQTSHPVLVFPPLPERGDFDLRKVLESE	YFFN 980
tr A0A6J1I1C4 A0A6J1I1C4_CUCMA	LLEDFTTYPGLTFPPLPERGNFDLREVLSK	YFFN 979
tr A0A6J1E061 A0A6J1E061_MOMCH	LLEGFETTYPGLTFPPLPERGDFDLREVLSN	YFFN 971
tr A0A0A0LH38 A0A0A0LH38_CUCSA	LLEGFETTYPGLTFPPLPERGDFDLQEVLSK	YFFN 975
tr A0A1S3BU26 A0A1S3BU26_CUCME	LLEGFETTYPGLTFPPLPERGDFNLQEVLSR	YFFN 975
tr A0A835UM73 A0A835UM73_VANPL	LLESFRKSFPTLSPPELPERGDFDLKEVLDSE	YFFN 1051
tr A0A4S8JC56 A0A4S8JC56_MUSBA	LLESFQQSFPPLTFPPLPERGDFDLKDVLESE	YFFN 1064
tr A0A445DB12 A0A445DB12_ARAHY	LLESFQGSFSTLMFPPLPDR	ETST 1008
tr A0A0E0QNF8 A0A0E0QNF8_ORYRU	LLESFEKSFPELKFPPPLPERGDFDLTDVLGSE	YFFN 983
tr A0A6P6BHY6 A0A6P6BHY6_DURZI	LLESFQKSFPSLNFPPPLPERGDFDLREVLESE	YFFN 996
tr A0A5E4F8X8 A0A5E4F8X8_PRUDU	LLEGFQQSFPPLTFPPLPERGDFDLRDVLESE	YFFN 1006
tr M5XKH1 M5XKH1_PRUPE	LLEGFQQSFPPLTFPPLPERGDFDLRDVLESE	YFFN 1006
tr A0A2C9WDN1 A0A2C9WDN1_MANES	LLESFEQSFPPLTFPPLPERGDFDLREVLESE	YFFN 1030
tr A0A6P6TN25 A0A6P6TN25_COFAR	LCRSGVTSILKMFWIPRISLTDI	YGN 1032
tr A0A1U7ZW01 A0A1U7ZW01_NELNU	LLESFQQSFPPLTFPPLPERGDFDLREVLDSE	YFFN 1031
tr D7SML3 D7SML3_VITVI	LLESFQQSFPFPALEFPPLPERGDFDLREVLESE	YFFN 1035

- | | |
|--|---|
| A0A251TQF3_HELAN, <i>Helianthus annuus</i> | A0A803MFE3_CHEQI, <i>Chenopodium quinoa</i> |
| A0A565CQ27_9BRAS <i>Arabis nemorensis</i> | V4L7M1_EUTSA, <i>Eutrema salsugineum</i> |
| R0HH96_9BRAS, <i>Capsella rubella</i> | O24600 RPOT3_ARATH, <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> |
| D7LGR7_ARALL, <i>Arabidopsis lyrata</i> subsp. <i>lyrata</i> | A0A078G6J8_BRANA, <i>Brassica napus</i> |
| A0A6J0K1N7_RAPSA, <i>Raphanus sativus</i> | A0A397Y433_BRACM, <i>Brassica campestris</i> |
| Q8L6J1 RPO3B_TOBAC, <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> | A0A1U8H8N9_CAPAN, <i>Capsicum annum</i> |
| A0A803QAW0_CANSA, <i>Cannabis sativa</i> | A0A5N6RVV2_9ROSI, <i>Carpinus fangiana</i> |
| A0A6J1I1C4_CUCMA, <i>Cucurbita maxima</i> | A0A6J1E061_MOMCH, <i>Momordica charantia</i> |
| A0A0A0LH38_CUCSA, <i>Cucumis sativus</i> | A0A1S3BU26_CUCME, <i>Cucumis melo</i> |
| A0A835UM73_VANPL, <i>Vanilla planifolia</i> | A0A4S8JC56_MUSBA, <i>Musa balbisiana</i> |
| A0A445DB12_ARAHY, <i>Arachis hypogaea</i> | A0A0E0QNF8_ORYRU, <i>Oryza rufipogon</i> |
| A0A6P6BHY6_DURZI, <i>Durio zibethinus</i> | A0A5E4F8X8_PRUDU, <i>Prunus dulcis</i> |
| M5XKH1_PRUPE, <i>Prunus persica</i> | A0A2C9WDN1_MANES, <i>Manihot esculenta</i> |
| A0A6P6TN25_COFAR, <i>Coffea Arabica</i> | A0A1U7ZW01_NELNU, <i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> |
| D7SML3_VITVI, <i>Vitis vinifera</i> | |

Figure 8 MSA of NEPs from the chloroplasts of various plant sources

3.7. Active Site Amino Acid Analyses of the DNA Polymerases and NEP of Plant Chloroplasts

Figure 9 shows the domain organization of the NEP of *A. thaliana* chloroplast. The NTD is not conserved whereas the other three regions are highly conserved.

Figure 9 Different domains of the NEP of chloroplasts (Numbering from the *A. thaliana* sequence)

The polymerase catalytic core region essentially contains three components, viz. a template-binding pair -YG-, a basic catalytic amino acid -K/R- and a nucleotide discriminating amino acid -R-, placed at -4 to -5 from the catalytic K/R. These three highly conserved components are found located in the NEP of the chloroplasts and as found in the chloroplast DNA pols IA and IB also (Figs. 2,3) The catalytic core regions are in close agreement with those already reported from other DNA/RNA polymerases (Table 2).

Table 2 Catalytic core regions of various RNA and DNA polymerases

Polymerase type	Catalytic core
SSU RNA/DNA pols	
Viral T7 SSU RNA pol	⁻⁶²⁰ WLA ⁸ Y ⁸ GVTR ⁴ SVTKR ¹ SVMTLAY ⁸ GS-
Viral SP6 SSU RNA Pol	⁻⁶¹² WDSI ⁸ GITR ⁴ SLTKK ¹ PVMTLPY ⁸ GS-
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (<i>Sc</i>)	⁻¹⁰⁰⁹ TR ⁴ KVVQK ¹ TVMTNVY ⁸ GV-
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (<i>H. sapiens</i>)	⁻⁹⁸⁶ TR ⁴ KVVQK ¹ TVMTVVY ⁸ GV-
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I (SSU)	⁻⁷⁵³ QR ⁴ RSAK ⁷⁵⁸ A ¹ INFLIY ⁸ GM-
Chloroplast SSU RNA pol (NEP) (<i>ARATH</i>)	⁻⁷⁶⁵ DR ⁴ KLVK ⁷⁷⁰ Q ¹ TVMTSVY ⁸ GV-
Chloroplast SSU DNA pol IA (<i>ARATH</i>)	⁻⁸⁷³ ER ⁴ RKAK ⁸⁷⁸ M ¹ LNFSIAY ⁸ GK-
Chloroplast SSU DNA pol IB (<i>ARATH</i>)	⁻⁸⁵⁷ ER ⁴ RKAK ⁸⁶² M ¹ LNFSIAY ⁸ GK-

Sc, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *ARATH*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*;

The active site amino acids, highlighted in dark blue, are confirmed by SDM analysis

3.8. Active Site Amino Acids at the DEDD(Y/H)-superfamily of PR Exonucleases in DNA Polymerases IA, IB and NEP of Plant Chloroplasts

The PR exonuclease active sites of NEPs from various plant chloroplasts are arrived at from the sequence similarity to other well-established DEDD-exonuclease superfamily as substantiated below. The DNA pols IA and IB use the DEDD(Y)-superfamily of exonuclease to PR the errors during chloroplast genome replication. The *E. coli* DNA pol I also uses the DEDD(Y)-superfamily PR exonuclease and its active site amino acids were confirmed both by SDM and X-ray crystallographic analyses by different investigators [31-33]. The *E. coli* DNA pol II also uses the -DEDD(Y)-superfamily and its active site amino acids were again confirmed both by SDM and X-ray crystallographic analyses by Wang and Yang [34]. They have shown that the amino acids 147 to 367 comprised the 3'→5' PR exonuclease domain and amino acids from 368 to 783 were involved in polymerase function. They found that the D³³⁵→N mutant of the active site lost its exonuclease activity and hence, suggested its involvement in the catalysis. The exonuclease active site amino acids of the pol II were further corroborated by the following (D¹⁵⁶→N, D²²⁹→N and D³³⁵→N) SDM exo- mutants [6] (Table 3). Furthermore, RNase D (EC 3.1.13.5), one of the seven exoribonucleases, which is involved in the 3'-maturation of several stable RNAs like tRNAs, 5S rRNA, and other small structured RNAs, was also shown to belong to the -DEDD(Y)-family [8]. Furthermore, the involvement of the DEDD(Y)-superfamily in PR exonuclease in the eukaryotic replicases, viz. DNA polymerases δ and ε from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* have been reported recently [35,36]. They found that the double mutant D²⁹⁰→A/E²⁹²→A (from the invariant first triad -D²⁹⁰xE²⁹²- of the DEDD(Y)-superfamily), was exonuclease deficient (Table 3). The replicative DNA polymerases δ and ε exhibit both polymerase and exonuclease activities [3].

Many of the PR exonucleases use DEDD(H)-superfamily. Fijalkowska and Schaaper [37] have found DEDD(H)-superfamily of PR exonuclease in the ε-subunits of the bacterial replicase multienzyme complexes (DNA pols III) belongs to the DnaQ-H-family with the four active site carboxylates (Asp¹², Glu¹⁴, Asp¹⁰³, and Asp¹⁶⁷) with the invariant His¹⁶², which acts as the general base in catalysis. They also found that modification of the two conserved amino acid residues, viz. Asp¹²→Ala and Glu¹⁴→Ala, in the ε-subunit by SDM experiments, resulted in the loss of the exonuclease function and hence, suggested that they might play a role in the coordination of the catalytic metal ion. These observations were further corroborated by X-ray crystallographic analysis of the ε-186 by Hamdan et al. [38].

3.9. PR Exonuclease Active Site Structure of the NEPs from Plant Chloroplasts

Figure 10 shows the proposed amino acids at the active site of the PR exonuclease of chloroplast NEPs. The active site is found to be very similar to the established active site of the ε-subunit of *E. coli* DNA pol III (Table 3) as both are coming from nuclear encoded.

NEP-PR Exonuclease ⁻⁵⁴⁵LRCD⁵⁴⁸VE⁵⁵⁰LKL-----NLD⁵⁷²F-----LNH⁵⁸⁶→3aa→D⁵⁹⁰LC⁵⁹²

Figure 10 Proposed amino acids at the PR exonuclease active site of the NEP from chloroplasts (the amino acids numberings are from the *A. thaliana*)

In all three exonucleases from the chloroplasts, the active site Tyr/His accepts the proton from the metal-bound water molecule to initiate catalysis, which is followed by the formation of a highly reactive Zn-hydroxyl free radical, leading to the removal of a misincorporated nucleotide. Thus, the 3'→5' exonuclease↔polymerase activities switch between excision and incorporation modes without dissociation of the enzyme-substrate complex [29].

Table 3 DEDD-superfamily of exonuclease active site amino acids from viral, bacterial, fungal, plant and animal sources

Exo-Family	Consensus A-site Pattern	Proton Acceptor	Catalytic Metal ion*	No. of Zn-binding site(s)
DEDD(Y/H)-family				
Prokaryotic PR Enzymes				
T4 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	-D ¹¹² X ¹¹⁴ E ²¹⁹ -Y ³²⁰ -D ³²⁴ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol I (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ³⁵⁵ X ³⁵⁷ E ⁴²⁴ -Y ⁴⁹⁷ -D ⁵⁰¹ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol II (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ¹⁵⁶ X ¹⁵⁸ E ²²⁹ -Y ³³¹ -D ³³⁵ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
RNase D (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ²⁸ X ³⁰ E ⁸⁵ -Y ¹⁵¹ -D ¹⁵⁵ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol III, ε-subunit (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ¹² X ¹⁴ -D ¹⁰³ -H ¹⁶² -D ¹⁶⁷ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
RNase T (<i>E. coli</i>)	-D ²³ X ²⁵ E ¹²⁵ -H ¹⁸¹ -D ¹⁸⁶ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in Eukaryotic DNA Replicases				
DNA pol ε cat. subunit (<i>S.c</i>)	-D ²⁹¹ X ²⁹² E ³⁸³ -Y ⁴⁷³ -D ⁴⁷⁷ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol δ cat. subunit (<i>H.s</i>)	-D ³¹⁶ X ³¹⁸ E ⁴⁰² -Y ⁵¹¹ -D ⁵¹⁵ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in DNA Polymerases 1A and 1B from Plant Chloroplasts				
DNA polymerase 1A (<i>ARATH</i>)	-DxE ²⁹⁶ -----D ³⁶⁶ -----Y ⁴⁷⁰ -D ⁴⁷⁴ -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA polymerase 1B (<i>ARATH</i>)	-DxE ²⁷² -----D ³⁴⁶ -----Y ⁴⁴⁸ -D ⁴⁵² -	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
PR Enzymes in RNA Polymerase, NEP from Plant Chloroplasts				
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	-DxE ⁵⁵⁰ -----D ⁵⁷² -----H ⁵⁸⁶ -D ⁵⁹⁰ -	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	-DxE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	-DxE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	-DxE-----D-----H-----D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1

Adapted from Palanivelu [7]

A-site, Active site; *Water-bound Zn²⁺; Active site amino acids confirmed by SDM are highlighted in dark blue and X-ray crystallography in light blue. *S.c*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *H.s*, *Homo sapiens*; *ARATH*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

Table 4 shows the DEDD-superfamily exonuclease active site amino acids and their distance conservations.

Table 4 DEDD-superfamily exonuclease active site amino acids and their distance conservations

DEDD-superfamily of PR exonucleases (-DxE-E-H*Y*--D*-)			
DNA Polymerases			
T4 DNA pol (E. coli Phage)	-D ¹¹⁴ E-----F ²¹⁵ D-----SY ³²⁸ N→3 aa-		D ³²⁴ VE- [40]
T7 DNA pol (E. coli Phage)	-D ¹ E ⁷ -----F ^{D235} D-----DY ¹⁷⁰ N→3 aa-		D ¹⁷⁴ VV-
Prokaryotic DNA Replicases (DNA pol III-ϵ-subunits)			
<i>E. coli</i>	-S ¹² TE-----F ^{D102} D-----LH ¹⁶² G→4 aa-		D ¹⁶⁷ AQ-
<i>Citrobacter amalonaticus</i>	-D ¹⁵ TE-----F ^{D105} D-----LH ¹⁶⁵ G→4 aa-		D ¹⁷⁰ AQ
<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	-D ¹² TE-----F ^{D102} D-----LH ¹⁶² G→4 aa-		D ¹⁶⁷ AQ
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	-D ¹² TE-----F ^{D102} D-----LH ¹⁶² G→4 aa-		D ¹⁶⁷ AQ
Eukaryotic DNA Replicases			
DNA pol ϵ cat. subunit (Sc)	-D ³⁵⁵ E-----F ^{D383} D-----EY ⁴⁷³ S→3 aa-		D ⁴⁷⁷ AV- [35,36]
DNA pol δ cat. subunit (Hs)	-D ¹¹⁵ E-----F ^{D492} D-----VY ⁵¹¹ C→3 aa-		D ⁵¹⁵ AY- [41]
DNA Polymerases IA from Plant Chloroplasts[#]			
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} S-----SY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ AI
<i>Chlorella desiccata</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} R-----SY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ AK
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} S-----FY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ SI
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} S-----SY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ AI
DNA Polymerases IB from Plant Chloroplasts[#]			
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} N-----SY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ SI
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} N-----CY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ SI
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} N-----SY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ SI
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	-D ²²⁸ TE-----F ^{D288} N-----SY ³²⁸ S→3 aa-		D ³²⁸ SI
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I Exo [#]	-D ³⁵⁵ TE-----Y ^{D428} D-----RY ⁴³⁷ A→3 aa-		D ⁵²⁵ AD-
SARS-CoVs[#]			
SARS-CoV-1 ExoN/ACE2	-S ¹ DVE-----D ²⁴³ D-----AH ²⁶⁸ V→4 aa-		D ²⁷⁵ AI-
MERS-CoV ExoN/DPP4	-S ¹ DVE-----D ²⁴³ D-----AH ²⁶⁸ V→4 aa-		D ²⁷⁵ AI-
SARS-CoV-2 ExoN/ACE2	-S ¹ DVE-----D ²⁴³ D-----AH ²⁶⁸ V→4 aa-		D ²⁷⁵ AI-
Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerase (NEP) from Plant Chloroplasts[#]			
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	-D ¹⁸⁸ VE-----LD ²¹² F-----NH ²⁵⁸ L→3 aa-		D ²⁶⁸ LC-
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	-D ¹⁸⁸ VE-----VD ²¹² F-----NH ²⁵⁸ L→3 aa-		D ²⁶⁸ LC-
<i>Onyza rufipogon</i>	-D ¹⁸⁸ VE-----LD ²¹² F-----NH ²⁵⁸ L→3 aa-		D ²⁶⁸ LC-
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	-D ¹⁸⁸ VE-----LD ²¹² F-----NH ²⁵⁸ L→3 aa-		D ²⁶⁸ LC-

Adapted from Palanivelu [7]. Sc, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; Hs, *Homo sapiens*.

*The distance between the proton acceptor (Y/H) and the last invariant D is 3 to 4 amino acids.

#Very similar active site amino acids are found in *E. coli* DNA pol I. ^Similar active site amino acids are found and confirmed by SDM in SARS-CoVs (6); ACE2, Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2; DPP4, Dipeptidyl peptidase 4. Active site amino acids confirmed by SDM analysis are highlighted in dark blue and by X-ray crystallography, are highlighted in light blue.

4. Conclusions

Chloroplast DNA polymerases IA and IB are highly homologous with 72.45% identity and possess very similar active sites for polymerization and proofreading functions. Their polymerization and proofreading active sites are very similar to the bacterial DNA polymerase I, suggesting their possible common evolutionary origin. However, the chloroplast DNA polymerases IA and IB differ from the bacterial DNA polymerase I by possessing a typical ZBM in them, as found in eukaryotic replicases. The ZBM is suggested to play a structural role. The polymerase catalytic cores of the DNA polymerases IA, IB and NEP are remarkably conserved. The proofreading exonucleases of all three polymerases (IA, IB and NEP) belong to the DEDD-superfamily. The DNA polymerases IA and IB belong to the DEDD(Y)- subfamily, whereas the NEP belongs to the DEDD(H)- subfamily.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to thank Dr. P. Sathiyamoorthy, Chief Scientist, GEM Research Foundation, Chennai, for useful suggestions on the manuscript.

References

- [1] Palanivelu P. DNA polymerases – An insight into their active sites and mechanism of action, In: Recent Advances in Biological Research, Vol 1, Chapter 2, pp 1-39, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK. ISBN: 9788193422441, DOI: 10.9734/bpi/rabr/v1; 2019.

- [2] Palanivelu P. Single Subunit RNA Polymerases: An Insight into their Active Sites and Catalytic Mechanism, In: *Advances and Trends in Biotechnology and Genetics*. Vol 1, Chapter 1, pp 1-38, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK. ISBN: 978-93-89246-59-9, DOI:10.9734/bpi/atbg/v1; 2019.
- [3] Palanivelu P. An Insight into the Mechanism of Genome Duplication in Eukaryotes: Polymerase and Proofreading Functions by Eukaryotic DNA Replicases. *Int J Rec Sci Res*. 13:2076-2116, (2022).
- [4] Palanivelu P. Multi-subunit RNA polymerases of bacteria - An insight into their active sites and catalytic mechanism. *Indian J Sci Technol*. 2018; 11: 1-37.
- [5] Palanivelu P. Active Sites of the Multi-subunit RNA Polymerases of Eubacteria and Chloroplasts are Similar in Structure and Function: Recent Perspectives. In: *Current Research Trends in Biological Science Vol. 2*. Chapter-3 pp 26-61, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK. Print ISBN: 978-93-90149-66-7, eBook ISBN: 978-93-90149-14-8, DOI: 10.9734/bpi/crtbs/v2;2020
- [6] Palanivelu P. An overview of the proofreading functions in bacteria and SARS-Coronaviruses. *Int J Biochem Res Rev*. 2021; 30: 33-62.
- [7] Palanivelu P. Identification of DEDD- and PHP-Superfamilies of Proofreading Exonucleases in the Acidic Protein Subunit PA of RNA Polymerase of Human Influenza Viruses, *World J Adv Res Rev*. 2022; 16: 804–824.
- [8] Zuo Y, Deutscher MP. Exoribonuclease superfamilies: structural analysis and phylogenetic distribution. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2001; 29:1017–1026
- [9] Nagpal S, Nair DT. The PHP domain of PolX from *Staphylococcus aureus* aids high fidelity DNA synthesis through the removal of misincorporated deoxyribo-, ribo- and oxidized nucleotides. *Nat Sci Rep*. 2021; 11:4178.
- [10] Timinskas K, Balvociute M, Timinskas A, Venclovas C. Comprehensive analysis of DNA polymerase III a subunits and their homologs in bacterial genomes. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2014; 42: 1393–1413.
- [11] Nielsen BL, Cupp JD, Brammer J (2010) Mechanisms for maintenance, replication, and repair of the chloroplast genome in plants. *J Exp Bot*. 61: 2535–2537.
- [12] Palanivelu P. Analyses of priming reactions and proofreading functions during initiation of replication of prokaryotic and eukaryotic genomes. *Brit J Pharma Med Res*. 2022; 7:3790-3828.
- [13] Morley SA, Nielsen BL. Chloroplast DNA Copy Number Changes during Plant Development in Organelle DNA Polymerase Mutants. *Front Plant Sci*. 2016, 7.
- [14] Parent JS, Lepage E, Brisson N. Divergent Roles for the Two PolI-Like Organelle DNA Polymerases of Arabidopsis. *Plant Physiol*. 2011, 156, 254–262.
- [15] Baruch-Torres N, Briebe LG. Plant organellar DNA polymerases are replicative and translesion DNA synthesis polymerases. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2017, 45, 10751–10763.
- [16] Sugiura M. The chloroplast genome. *Essays Biochem*. 1995, 30, 49–57.
- [17] Serino G, Maliga P. RNA polymerase subunits encoded by the plastid *rpo* genes are not shared with the nucleus-encoded plastid enzyme. *Plant Physiol*. 1998; 117:1165-1170.
- [18] Timmis JN, Ayliffe MA, Huang CY, Martin W. Endosymbiotic gene transfer: Organelle genomes forge eukaryotic chromosomes. *Nat Rev Genet*. 2004; 5:123–135.
- [19] Fukuzawa H, Kohchi T, Sano T, Nakahigashi K, Umesono K. Cold spring harbor symposium for quantitative biology. 1987; 52:791-804.
- [20] Hedtke B, Börner T, Weihe A. Mitochondrial and chloroplast phage-type RNA polymerase in Arabidopsis. *Science*, 1997;277:809–811. 11.
- [21] Hajdukiewicz PT, Allison LA, Maliga P. The two RNA polymerases encoded by the nuclear and the plastid compartments transcribe distinct groups of genes in tobacco plastids. *EMBO J*. 1997; 16:4041–4048. 12.
- [22] Allison LA, Simon LD, Maliga P. Deletion of *rpoB* reveals a second distinct transcription system in plastids of higher plants. *EMBO J*. 1996; 15:2802–2809.
- [23] Maciossek G, Kofer W, Bock A, Schoch S, Maier RM, Wanner G, Rudiger W, Koop HU, Herrmann RG. Targeted disruption of the plastid RNA polymerase genes *rpoA*, *B* and *C1*: molecular biology, biochemistry and ultrastructure. *Plant J*. 1999; 18:477–489.

- [24] Severinov K, Mustaev A, Kukarini A, Muzzin O, Little MC, Hallick RB. Chloroplast rpoA, rpoB, and rpoC Genes Specify at least Three Components of a Chloroplast DNA-dependent RNA polymerase active in tRNA and mRNA Transcription. *J Biol Chem*. 1998; 263:14302-14307.
- [25] Allison LA. The role of sigma factors in plastid transcription. *Biochimie*. 2000; 82: 537–548.
- [26] Gruissem W, Zurawski G. Analysis of promoter regions for the spinach chloroplast rbcl, atpB and psbA genes. *EMBO J*. 1985; 4: 3375-3383.
- [27] Gruissem W, Zurawski G. Identification and mutational analysis of the promoter for a spinach chloroplast transfer RNA gene. *EMBO J*. 1985; 4:1637–1644.
- [28] Reha-Krantz LJ, R L Nonay RL. Genetic and biochemical studies of bacteriophage T4 DNA polymerase 3'-->5'-exonuclease activity. *J Biol Chem*. 1993; 268:27100-27108.
- [29] Mizrahi V, Benkovic P, Benkovic SJ. Mechanism of DNA polymerase I: exonuclease/ polymerase activity switch and DNA sequence dependence of pyrophosphorolysis and misincorporation reactions. *Proc Natl Acad Sci, (USA)*. 1986; 83:5769-5773.
- [30] Palanivelu P. An Insight into the Active Sites of the Catalytic Basic Protein Subunit PB1 of the RNA Polymerase of Human Influenza Viruses, *World J Adv Res Rev*. 17: 625–565 (2022).
- [31] Derbyshire V, Freemont PS, Sanderson MR, Beese L, Friedman JM, Joyce CM, Steitz TA. Genetic and crystallographic studies of the 3,5"-exonucleolytic site of DNA polymerase I. *Science*. 1988;240: 199-201.
- [32] Derbyshire V, Grindley ND, Joyce CM. The 3'-5' exonuclease of DNA polymerase I of Escherichia coli: contribution of each amino acid at the active site to the reaction. *EMBO J*. 1991; 10:17-24.
- [33] Joyce CM, Steitz TA. DNA polymerase I: From crystal structure to function via genetics. *Trends Biochem Sci*. 1987;12: 288-292.
- [34] Wang F, Yang W. Structural insight into translesion synthesis by DNA Pol II. *Cell*. 2009; 139:1279–1289.
- [35] Pinto MN, ter Beek J, Ekanger LA, Erik Johansson E, Barton JK. The [4Fe4S] Cluster of Yeast DNA Polymerase ϵ Is Redox Active and Can Undergo DNA-Mediated Signaling. *J Am Chem Soc*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.1c07150>
- [36] Jain R, Rajashankar KR, Buku A, Johnson RE, Prakash L, Prakash S, et al. Crystal structure of yeast DNA polymerase epsilon catalytic domain. *PLoS ONE*. 2014; 9:e94835. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0094835.
- [37] Fijalkowska IJ, Schaaper RM. Mutants in the Exo I motif of Escherichia coli dnaQ: Defective proofreading and in viability due to error catastrophe. *Proc Natl Acad Sci. (USA)*. 1996; 93:2856-2861.
- [38] Hamdan S, Carr PD, Brown SE, Ollis DL, Dixon NE. Structural Basis for Proofreading during Replication of the Escherichia coli Chromosome. *Structure*. 2002; 10:535–546.
- [39] Zuo Y, Zheng H, Wang Y, Chruszcz M, Cymborowski M, Skarina T, Savchenko A, Malhotra A, Minor W. Crystal Structure of RNase T, an exoribonuclease involved in tRNA maturation and end-turnover. *Structure*. 2007; 15:417–428.
- [40] Maksimova TG, Mustayev AA, Zaychikov EF, Lyakhov DL, Tunitskaya VL, Akbarov AK, Luchin SV, et al. Lys631 residue in the active site of the bacteriophage T7 RNA polymerase. Affinity labeling and site-directed mutagenesis. *Eur J Biochem*. 1991; 195:841-847.
- [41] Pavlov YI, Maki S, Maki H, Kunkel TA. Evidence for interplay among yeast replicative DNA polymerases alpha, delta and epsilon from studies of exonuclease and polymerase active site mutations. *BMC Biol*. 2004; 2:1-13.